

SEEDS | science by teenagers for teenagers

How to empower teens to manage their health

a guide for teachers and educators

This guide

fostering healthy lifestyles in teens

Teen bodies are going through **many physical changes** that need to be supported by healthy behavior and a balanced diet. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), teenagers establish patterns of behavior — related to diet, physical activity, substance use, and sexual activity — that can protect their **health** and the health of others around them, or put their health at risk now and in the future.

your role as a teacher and educator

Health and education are intrinsically **related**. As we improve one, we improve the other. This guide provides information on four important areas in teen lives: 1. healthy **snacking**, 2. **physical activity**, 3. **sedentary behavior**, and 4. **screen time**. This guide also offers suggestions and **practical tips** that you as a teacher can use on a daily basis to help empower your students.

What is SEEDS

extreme citizen science

SEEDS (Science Engagement to Empower aDolescentS) is a **science project by teenagers for teenagers**. It aims to empower teens to live healthy lifestyles and to help them explore the importance and excitement of science. This is achieved with an approach called **extreme citizen science**, based on the participation of **leader adolescents in all the research processes**: 1. **analysis** of adolescents' barriers and needs for conducting a healthy lifestyles, 2. designing a community-based public **intervention**

for adolescents of low-socioeconomic areas and with potential stakeholders participation, 3. analysis of **data** 4. and **dissemination** to community. SEEDS is based in **four countries**, Greece, Spain, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. Each country included schools and a professional partner. To assist with the overall project, the City of Rotterdam and European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) were involved. More here: seedsmakeathons.com/

Citizen science

Citizen science

a new alliance

Citizen science is a collaboration, at different levels of **involvement, by the public in scientific investigation and data collection**. A citizen science project can involve one person or millions working together towards a common goal. Projects of citizen science can be devised in **various fields**, typically ecology, astronomy, medicine, computer science, statistics, psychology, genetics, and also in social science, humanities and the arts. The larger projects that can occur through citizen science allow investigations at wider scales — leading to **discoveries** that a single scientist or group could never achieve alone. These projects can even help to design **new directions in research**.

citizen science in education

Citizen science is a growing and promising field. Its potential for education is open to the collaboration between schools and scientists. As projects are developed, new knowledge and awareness on the practices and methods of research are generated.

Citizen science has great potential for schools. It allows **direct involvement of students** and facilitates the connection between science and their **life experience**. It develops critical thinking and field learning of the scientific methods and establishes **an authentic connection** with the world of research through actual projects. **Teachers have a more active role** which allows you to avoid the old educational model of mere transmission of knowledge. Instead, you become a participant in a modernized and **active educational community**. All this allows schools to play a more active role in the educational ecosystem as proposed by the most recent European indications promoting open schooling.

Fact sheets

Teens and health

your role as teacher

Teenagers are often oblivious to their health and do not think about the long-term consequences of their present behavioral patterns. Sleep, nutrition, substances, addictions, and mental health are just some of the issues on which to focus attention. As educators and teachers, you are an important **point of reference** for teens. You can do a lot to empower young people and help them become more aware. It is **awareness that is the first step** towards more responsible choices. In this guide you will find basic information and some suggestions about how to **help teens on a daily basis**.

fact sheet: healthy snacks

Teenagers eat irregularly and often choose unhealthy, high-fat, highly processed foods.

Snacks are eaten between main meals and provide us the nutrients and energy that our bodies need throughout the day, as well as reduce the feeling of fatigue and improve concentration levels.

As teachers and educators, it is certainly difficult to **prevent your students from consuming unhealthy snacks** or energy drinks.

Some suggestions to use daily:

- **reduce** the frequency of consumption
- bring some **good examples** to class
- read the **ingredients** together
- read the **nutrition labels** together
- make up some **discussion topics** and reflect on the subject together during class time.

fact sheet: physical activity

Regular physical activity during adolescence prevents and mitigates symptoms of depression and anxiety, prevents hormonal imbalances, and ensures a healthy body composition and proper physical development. It also benefits memory retention, concentration levels, and attention span.

With academic pressure increasing in today's schools, it is **easy to substitute sporting activities for supplemental academic ones**. The implications can be quite **negative**, regarding physical health and academic performance.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescents should do, on average, at least **60 minutes** of moderate-to-vigorous exercises, mostly aerobic, **everyday**. Workouts also should incorporate vigorous-intensity aerobic activities, as well as those that strengthen muscle and bone, at least 3 days per week.

fact sheet: sedentary behavior

Avoid sedentary behavior by finding enjoyable ways to be active. Physical activity refers to all movement: walking, cycling, wheeling, organized sports, active recreation, playing — at any skill level.

The World Health Organization calculates that 81% of **adolescents do not do enough physical activity**. As a teacher you can encourage your students to limit the amount of time spent being sedentary, particularly the amount of recreational screen time.

Beyond suggesting your students to engage in sports activities, you can:

- dedicate **5-10 minutes per class** to physical activities
- perform some of your **classes outdoor**.

fact sheet: screen time

Time spent in front of a screen affects health. Dry eyes, itchy eyes, blurry vision, and headaches are often the case. Prolonged screen time diminishes opportunities for physical activity and can take away time from sleep. In the end it can affect emotional stability.

COVID-19 has brought to the fore the need to **rethink the concept of screen time** from a health perspective. Internet and internet-enabled devices have become **important tools** for learning, socializing and connecting with peers and relatives.

As teachers you can help your students to **become aware of the reasons for using online technology** in the learning process and in their lives. Talk together about age appropriate content and context. Make an in-class study of the online and offline life and what the optimum balance would be.

Info

Further reading

Practical tools, SEEDS project, <https://seedsmakeathons.com/category/practical-tools/>

Healthy eating for teens, National Health System UK, <https://www.nhs.uk/live-well/eat-well/healthy-eating-for-teens/>

Healthy diet, World Health Organization, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/healthy-diet>

Adolescents Health, World Health Organization, https://www.who.int/health-topics/adolescent-health#tab=tab_1

Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health, World Health Organization, <https://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/physical-activity-recommendations-5-17years.pdf>

The SEEDS team

who we are

A group of nutrition, public health, physical activity and citizen science experts, working across Europe to explore how the SEEDS approach can help improve healthy lifestyles and STEM interest in teenagers.

Website: www.seedsmakeathons.com

Twitter: @SMakeathons

Email: upi@iispv.cat

